

Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of the Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve, South Africa

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ABSTRACT: As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), surveys were undertaken in the Eastern Cape. In this paper, an annotated species list of spider species sampled from the Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve is presented. A total of 48 families represented by 190 species from 133 genera have been recorded. The most species-rich families are the Thomisidae (27 spp.), Araneidae (22 spp.), and Salticidae (19 spp.), with 22 singletons. The conservation status and level of endemism based on their known distribution are provided for each species. Eight of the species were not evaluated and five of them are possibly new to science. Eight species are endemic to the Eastern Cape and three are Baviaanskloof endemics. Only one species is of special concern and three species are endemic to the reserve. Six species are Data Deficient and one Endangered but 92.1% of the species have a wide distribution with no known threats and are listed as Least Concern. **Keywords:** biodiversity, conservation assessment, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

Spiders have been sampled from 195 sites in the Eastern Cape, as part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) but large areas still need to be sampled. A total of 837 species, 38.6% of all South African species, have been recorded from the province so far.

We report here on the first SANSa survey on the spider fauna of the Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve (BMR). It is a protected area in the Eastern Cape province and was declared a World Heritage Site in 2004 and is one of the richest plant regions in the world. The BMR includes a cluster of formally protected areas managed by the Eastern Cape Parks Board totaling around 5 530 000 hectares. It includes the Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve, the Groendal Nature Reserve, and Formosa Nature Reserve, as well as private land.

A checklist of the 190 species is presented with information on the global distribution, endemism, and conservation status of each of the species recorded.

METHODS

Study area: The Baviaanskloof, or “Valley of Baboons”, is a 75-km long valley, of varying width, that lies between the parallel east-west running Baviaanskloof and Kouga mountain ranges in the western region of the Eastern Cape province (33°30'S 24°8'E). The eastern-most point of the valley is some 95 km north-west of the coastal city of Port Elizabeth, and its most southerly point is 50 km from the Indian Ocean (Fig. 4). Baviaanskloof is remarkable in terms of the diversity of its natural ecosystems. Seven of South Africa's eight biomes are represented here including Fynbos, Forest, Grassland, Succulent Karoo, Nama-karoo, sub-tropical thicket and savanna. On the northern slopes are the Spekboomveld and Valley Bushveld. On the southern slopes flourishes the Cape Fynbos and in the valleys there is a concentrated of Knysna Forest vegetation. On the mountain plateaus are the Rhinoceros Veldt and Grassland. The widespread succulent Karoo bush in the valley is probably why the Baviaanskloof is classified as a part of the Little Karoo (Figs 1–3).

Surveys, identification, photography, and voucher specimens: Several surveys were undertaken in the BMR. The second author (LW), with members of the Spider Club of Southern Africa, as well as members of the public participating in a SANSa survey during the Easter weekend in 2008, sampled more than 500 specimens. LW paid a second visit to the area sampling and photographing spiders. Collected specimens of both trips were identified in Pretoria by the

Figures 1–3. Different vegetation types found at the Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve. Photo credits: 1. From web. 2 & 3. Linda Wiese.

first author and voucher specimens are housed at the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria. The third author (LL) surveyed the area in February (2008) and the identified voucher specimens are housed in the National Museum in Bloemfontein.

Figure 4: Map of the Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve. After Htoni.

Endemicity: The endemicity values for each species are provided in Appendix 1 based on their currently known distribution. Seven endemicity categories are recognised:

- 6 – known only from BMR.
- 5 – endemic to the Eastern Cape province (ECE) but wider than the type locality.
- 4 – endemic to South Africa (SAE) but known from only two adjoining provinces.
- 3 – South African endemic (SAE) known from more than two provinces or two provinces not adjoining.
- 2 – endemic to Southern Africa (STHE).
- 1 – endemic to the Afrotropical Region (AE).
- 0 – cosmopolitan, Africa and wider.

Conservation status: As part of the Red Listing Spider Project (Foord *et al.*, 2020), the preliminary conservation status of species was determined. Immatures, new species, and undetermined taxa were not evaluated (NE). Species with a broad distribution (categories 0–2) were considered to be of Least Concern (LC); those of categories 3 and 4 were considered to be South African endemics (SAE), and many of them are also LC; while species of special concern usually belong to categories 5 or 6.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: A total of 48 families represented by 190 species from 133 genera have been recorded (Table 1). Eight species could not be identified to species level as their taxonomy is unresolved or they could be new to science (Table 2, Appendix 1).

The 190 species collected fall within the range of species reported from other Eastern Cape areas such as the 132 spp. from Mkhambathi Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011), 151 spp. from Jeffreys Bay (Wiese & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2023) and 276 spp. from the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020).

Family diversity: The most species-rich families are the Thomisidae (27 spp.), Araneidae (22 spp.), and Salticidae (19 spp.) with 23 families known from only a single species. The same three families were also the most species rich in the three surveys mentioned above.

Conservation status: Of the 190 species sampled, six species (3.2%) are data deficient (DD), i.e., lacking taxonomic or distribution data, while eight species (4.2%) were not evaluated (NE) (Table 2; Appendix 1) of which six might be new to science. The majority of the species (175 spp., 92.1%) are listed as being of least concern (LC). Only the zodariid *Procydrela precursor* Jocqué, 1999 is presently listed as Endangered due to restricted distribution.

TABLE 1: Spider diversity of the Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve (BMR) with total number of families, genera (GEN) and species (SPP.) sampled.

FAMILIES	GEN	SPP.	FAMILIES	GEN	SPP.
Agelenidae	1	2	Nephilidae	1	2
Amaurobiidae	1	1	Oonopidae	1	1
Araneidae	14	22	Oxyopidae	3	10
Bemmeridae	1	1	Palpimanidae	1	1
Caponiidae	1	1	Philodromidae	4	6
Cheiracanthiidae	2	3	Pholcidae	2	3
Clubionidae	1	1	Phyxelididae	1	2
Corinnidae	2	2	Pisauridae	7	7
Ctenidae	1	1	Salticidae	12	19
Cyatholipidae	1	1	Scytodidae	1	1
Cyrtacheniidae	1	1	Segestriidae	1	1
Dictynidae	2	2	Selenopidae	1	3
Deinopidae	1	1	Sicariidae	1	1
Eresidae	1	1	Sparassidae	1	1
Euagridae	1	1	Stasimopidae	1	1
Galliellidae	1	2	Tetragnathidae	2	6
Gnaphosidae	7	13	Theraphosidae	1	1
Hahniidae	1	1	Theridiidae	6	7
Linyphiidae	3	3	Thomisidae	15	27
Lycosidae	8	10	Trachelidae	3	3
Migidae	2	2	Trochanteriidae	1	1
Mimetidae	2	2	Uloboridae	4	4
Miturgidae	1	1	Zodariidae	4	4
Mysmenidae	1	1	Zoropsidae	2	2
			48	133	190

Species endemicity: A large percentage of species have a wide distribution and 72 species (37.9%) are African endemics (Table 2) and a total of 21 species (11.1%) are found wider than Africa. Thirty-three species are Southern African endemics but the largest number of species (57) recorded are endemic to South Africa.

TABLE 2: Conservation status and endemicity of the spider species sampled at the Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve (BMR).

CONSERVATION STATUS	NO SPP.	%
Not Evaluated (NE)	9	4.7
Data Deficient (DD)	6	3.2
Least Concern (LC)	174	91.6
Endangered	1	0.5
ENDEMICITY		
0 – Africa and wider (C)	21	11.1
1 – Africa endemics (AE)	72	37.9
2 – Southern African endemics (STHE)	32	16.8
3 – South African endemics (SAE)	34	17.8
4 – South African endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	15	7.9
5 – Eastern Cape endemics (ECE)	5	2.6
6 – Known only from type locality BMR	3	1.5

Eight species are Eastern Cape endemics: *Zelotes resolution* FitzPatrick, 2007 (Gnaphosidae); *Proevippa dregei* (Purcell, 1903), *Trabea nigriceps* Purcell, 1903 (Lycosidae); *Anyphops schoenlandi* (Pocock, 1902) (Selenopidae) and *Stasimopus schoenlandi* Pocock, 1900 (Stasimopidae). Three species are endemic to the BMR: *Cheiramiona baviaan* Lotz, 2015, *Drassodella baviaans* Mbo & Haddad, 2019 (Fig. 8) and *D. trilineata* Mbo & Haddad, 2019. All three species are known only from one sex and due to the restricted range listed as Data Deficient.

CONCLUSION

Each survey contributes to our knowledge on the geographical distribution of spider species. Although this paper probably represents only a portion of the spider fauna present, we hope this information will stimulate further interest and research. The contribution of existing reserves can only be highlighted through studies such as this.

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Figures 5–8. Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve. 5–7. New species. 5. *Clubiona* sp. (Clubionidae). 6. *Spiroctenus* sp. (Bemmeridae). 7. *Philodromus* sp. (Philodromidae). Baviaanskloof endemic. 8. *Drassodella baviaans*.

Figures 9–23. Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve. 9. *Pararaneus perforatus* (Araneidae). 10. *Cheiramiona baviaan* (Cheiracanthiidae). 11. *Clubiona* sp. (Clubionidae). 12. *Scytodes elizabethae* (Scytodidae). 13. *Ctenus pulchriventris* (Ctenidae). 14. *Drassodella baviaans* (Gallieniellidae). 15. *Pardosa manubriata* (Lycosidae). 16. *Pardosa crassipalpis* (Lycosidae). Oxyopidae: 17. *Oxyopes flavipalpis*. 18. *Oxyopes russoi*. 19. *Peucetia nicolae*. Philodromidae: 20. *Philodromus brachycephalus*. 21. *Thanatus vulgaris*. 22. *Vidole capensis* (Phyxelididae). 23. *Cispius kimbius* (Pisauridae). Photo credits: Linda Wiese.

Figures 24–38. Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve. Salticidae: 24. *Heliophanus hastatus*. 25. *Heliophanus modicus*. Thomisidae: 26. *Holopelus almaiae*. 27. *Thomisus australis*. 28. *Thomisus daradioides*. 29. *Runcinia aethiops*. 30. *Synema diana*. 31. *Synema mandibulare*. 32. *Xysticus havilandi*. 33. *Tetragnatha bogotensis* (Tetragnathidae). Zoropsideae: 34. *Griswoldia urbensis*. 35. *Phanotea xhosa*. Uloboridae: 36. *Zosis geniculata*. 37. *Uloborus* sp. new. 38. *Isela okuncana* (Mysmenidae). Photo credits: 24–37. Linda Wiese. 38. Leon Lotz.

APPENDIX 1: Spiders of Baviaanskloof Mega Reserve listing their endemism (END), conservation status (CON), and country endemism (CEND).

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
Agelenidae	<i>Benoitia ocellata</i> (Pocock, 1900)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Benoitia raymondeae</i> (Lessert, 1915)	1	LC	AE
Amaurobiidae	<i>Pseudauximus</i> sp.*		NE	
Araneidae	<i>Araneus apricus</i> (Karsch, 1884)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Araneus nigroquadratus</i> Lawrence, 1937	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Argiope trifasciata</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C
	<i>Caerostris sexcuspidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C
	<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C
	<i>Eriovixia excelsa</i> (Simon, 1889)	0	LC	C
	<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C.L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE
	<i>Gasteracantha versicolor</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Gea infuscata</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE
	<i>Ideocaira triquetra</i> Simon, 1903	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Isoxya cicatricosa</i> (C.L. Koch, 1844)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Isoxya tabulata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Nemoscolus elongatus</i> Lawrence, 1947	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Nemoscolus tubicola</i> (Simon, 1887)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona novella</i> (Simon, 1907)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	0	LC	C
	<i>Neoscona triangula</i> (Keyserling, 1864)	0	LC	C
<i>Pararaneus perforatus</i> (Thorell, 1899) (Fig. 9)	1	LC	AE	
<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	
Bemmeridae	<i>Spiroctenus</i> sp.* (Fig. 6 & 12)		NE	
Caponiidae	<i>Caponia capensis</i> Purcell, 1904	2	LC	STHE
Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiracanthium furculatum</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cheiramiona baviaan</i> Lotz, 2015 (Fig. 10)	6	DD	SAE
	<i>Cheiramiona filipes</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
Clubionidae	<i>Clubiona</i> sp.* (Figs 5 & 11)		NE	
Corinnidae	<i>Coenoptychus tropicalis</i> (Haddad, 2004)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pronophaea natalica</i> Simon, 1897	3	LC	SAE
Ctenidae	<i>Ctenus pulchriiventris</i> (Simon, 1897) (Fig. 13)	2	LC	STHE
Cyatholipidae	<i>Cyatholipus quadrimaculatus</i> Simon, 1894	4	LC	SAE
Cyrtoucheniidae	<i>Ancylotrypa</i> sp.*		NE	
Deinopidae	<i>Menneus camelus</i> Pocock, 1902	3	LC	SAE
Dictynidae	<i>Archeodictyna</i> sp.		NE	
	<i>Mashimo leleupi</i> Lehtinen, 1967	1	LC	AE
Eresidae	<i>Gandanameno spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1900)	2	LC	STHE
Euagridae	<i>Allothelie australis</i> (Purcell, 1903)	4	LC	SAE
Gallieniellidae	<i>Drassodella baviaans</i> Mbo & Haddad, 2019 (Fig. 14)	6	DD	SAE
	<i>Drassodella trilineata</i> Mbo & Haddad, 2019	6	DD	SAE
Gnaphosidae	<i>Ammoxenus pentheri</i> Simon, 1896	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Asemesthes reflexus</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Camillina biplagia</i> Tucker, 1923	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Drassodes lophognathus</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Trephopoda kannemeyeri</i> (Tucker, 1923)	3	LC	SAE

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
	<i>Xerophaeus appendiculatus</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Xerophaeus communis</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Zelotes albanicus</i> (Hewitt, 1915)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Zelotes invidus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes natalensis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zelotes resolution</i> FitzPatrick, 2007	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Zelotes scrutatus</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872)	1	LC	AE
Hahniidae	<i>Hahnia tabulicola</i> Simon, 1898	1	LC	AE
Linyphiidae	<i>Agyneta habra</i> (Locket, 1968)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Microlinyphia sterilis</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Typhistes gloriosus</i> Jocqué, 1984	3	LC	SAE
Lycosidae	<i>Allocosa tuberculipalpa</i> (Caporiacco, 1940)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Arctosa nivosa</i> (Purcell, 1903)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Foveosa foveolata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hogna bimaculata</i> (Purcell, 1903)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Pardosa crassipalpis</i> Purcell, 1903 (Fig. 16)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa biampliata</i> (Purcell, 1903) (Fig. 15)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Proevippa dregei</i> (Purcell, 1903)	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Trabea nigriceps</i> Purcell, 1903	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Trabea purcelli</i> Roewer, 1951	1	LC	AE
Migidae	<i>Moggridgea peringueyi</i> Simon, 1903	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Poecilomigas abrahami</i> (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1889)	2	LC	STHE
Mimetidae	<i>Anansi natalensis</i> (Lawrence, 1938)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Ero capensis</i> Simon, 1895	2	LC	STHE
Miturgidae	<i>Parapostenus hewitti</i> Lessert, 1923	3	LC	SAE
Mysmenidae	<i>Isela okuncana</i> Griswold, 1985 (Fig.38)	4	DD	SAE
Nephilidae	<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> (Thorell, 1859)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Trichonephila inaurata madagascariensis</i> (Vinson, 1863)	1	LC	AE
Oonopidae	<i>Australoonops granulatus</i> Hewitt, 1915	3	LC	SAE
Oxyopidae	<i>Hamataliwa rostrifrons</i> (Lawrence, 1928)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Hamataliwa fronticornis</i> (Lessert, 1927)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes affinis</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes flavipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858) (Fig. 17)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes longispinosus</i> Lawrence, 1938	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Oxyopes russoi</i> Caporiacco, 1940 (Fig. 18)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxyopes</i> morpho sp. 3		NE	
	<i>Peucetia maculifera</i> Pocock, 1900	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Peucetia nicolae</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1994 (Fig. 19)	3	LC	SAE
Palpimanidae	<i>Palpimanus capensis</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE
Philodromidae	<i>Hirriusa arenacea</i> (Lawrence, 1927)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Philodromus brachycephalus</i> Lawrence, 1952 (Fig. 20)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Philodromus guineensis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
	<i>Philodromus</i> sp.* (Fig. 7)		NE	
	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870 (Fig. 21)	0	LC	C
	<i>Tibellus minor</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
Pholcidae	<i>Quamtana vidal</i> Huber, 2003	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Smeringopus natalensis</i> Lawrence, 1947	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Smeringopus ubicki</i> Huber, 2012	4	LC	SAE

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
Phyxelididae	<i>Vidole capensis</i> (Pocock, 1900) (Fig. 22)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Vidole schreineri</i> (Purcell, 1904)	3	LC	SAE
Pisauridae	<i>Afropisaura ducis</i> (Strand, 1913)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Chiasmopes lineatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Cispus kimbis</i> Blandin, 1978 (Fig. 23)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Euprosthénopsis pulchella</i> (Pocock, 1902)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Maypacijs bilineatus</i> (Pavesi, 1895)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Nilus massajae</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
Salticidae	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Brancus mustelus</i> (Simon, 1902)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Dendryphantes purcelli</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Evarcha denticulata</i> Wesolowska & Haddad, 2013	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE
	<i>Heliophanus hastatus</i> Wesolowska, 1986 (Fig. 24)	1	LC	STHE
	<i>Heliophanus modicus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903 (Fig. 25)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Hyllus argyrotoxis</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE
	<i>Langona warchalowskii</i> Wesolowska, 2007	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Massagris honesta</i> Wesolowska, 1993	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Massagris mirifica</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Portia schultzi</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene coccineovittata</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstaecker, 1873)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyene ogdeni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thyenula aurantiaca</i> (Simon, 1902)	2	LC	STHE
	Scytodidae	<i>Scytodes elizabethae</i> Purcell, 1904 (Fig. 14)	3	LC
Segestriidae	<i>Ariadna lightfooti</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
Selenopidae	<i>Anyphops braunsi</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Anyphops schoenlandi</i> (Pocock, 1902)	5	LC	SAE
	<i>Anyphops spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1896)	3	LC	SAE
Sicariidae	<i>Loxosceles spinulosa</i> Purcell, 1904	4	LC	SAE
Sparassidae	<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE
Stasimopidae	<i>Stasimopus schoenlandi</i> Pocock, 1900	5	DD	SAE
Tetragnathidae	<i>Leucauge decorata</i> (Blackwall, 1864)	0	LC	C
	<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Leucauge levanderi</i> (Kulczynski, 1901)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tetragnatha bogotensis</i> Keyserling, 1865	0	LC	C
	<i>Tetragnatha ceylonica</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1869	0	LC	C
	<i>Tetragnatha nitens</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C
Theraphosidae	<i>Harpactira tigrina</i> Ausserer, 1875	4	LC	SAE
Theridiidae	<i>Euryopsis funebris</i> (Hentz, 1850)	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus cinctus</i> Blackwall, 1865	0	LC	C
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C
	<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	0	LC	C
	<i>Platnickina mneon</i> (Bösenberg & Strand, 1906)	0	LC	C
	<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND	
Phyxelididae	<i>Vidole capensis</i> (Pocock, 1900)	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Vidole schreineri</i> (Purcell, 1904)	3	LC	SAE	
Pisauridae	<i>Afropisaura ducis</i> (Strand, 1913)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Chiasmopes lineatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Cispius kimbius</i> Blandin, 1978	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Euprostenopsis pulchella</i> (Pocock, 1902)	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Maypacijs bilineatus</i> (Pavesi, 1895)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Nilus massajae</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	
Salticidae	<i>Brancus mustelus</i> (Simon, 1902)	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Cyrba nigrimana</i> Simon, 1900	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Dendryphantes purcelli</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Evarcha denticulata</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2013	4	LC	SAE	
	<i>Evarcha prosimilis</i> Wesolowska & Cumming, 2008	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Heliophanus hastatus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	STHE	
	<i>Heliophanus modicus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Hyllus argyrotexus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Langona warchalowskii</i> Wesolowska, 2007	2	LC	STHE	
	<i>Massagris honesta</i> Wesolowska, 1993	4	LC	SAE	
	<i>Massagris mirifica</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Natta chionogaster</i> (Simon, 1901)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Portia schultzi</i> Karsch, 1878	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thyene coccineovittata</i> (Simon, 1885)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thyene ogdeni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Thyenula aurantiaca</i> (Simon, 1902)	2	LC	STHE	
	Scytodidae	<i>Scytodes elizabethae</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
	Segestriidae	<i>Ariadna lightfooti</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE
Selenopidae	<i>Anyphops braunsi</i> (Lawrence, 1940)	3	LC	SAE	
	<i>Anyphops schoenlandi</i> (Pocock, 1902)	5	LC	SAE	
	<i>Anyphops spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1896)	3	LC	SAE	
Sicariidae	<i>Loxosceles spinulosa</i> Purcell, 1904	4	LC	SAE	
Sparassidae	<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE	
Stasimopidae	<i>Stasimopus schoenlandi</i> Pocock, 1900	5	DD	SAE	
Tetragnathidae	<i>Leucauge decorata</i> (Blackwall, 1864)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Leucauge levanderi</i> (Kulczynski, 1901)	1	LC	AE	
	<i>Tetragnatha bogotensis</i> Keyserling, 1865 (Fig. 33)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Tetragnatha ceylonica</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1869	0	LC	C	
	<i>Tetragnatha nitens</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Harpactira tigrina</i> Ausserer, 1875	4	LC	SAE	
Theraphosidae	<i>Euryopsis funebris</i> (Hentz, 1850)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Latrodectus cinctus</i> Blackwall, 1865	0	LC	C	
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	0	LC	C	
	<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Platnickina mneon</i> (Bösenberg & Strand, 1906)	0	LC	C	
	<i>Steatoda capensis</i> Hann, 1990	0	LC	C	
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE	

FAMILIES	SPECIES	END	CON	CEND
Thomisidae	<i>Diaea puncta</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE
	<i>Geraesta congoensis</i> (Lessert, 1943)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Holopelus almiae</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1986 (Fig. 26)	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Heriaeus crassispinus</i> Lawrence, 1942	1	LC	AE
	<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE
	<i>Parabomis martini</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
	<i>Monaeses paradoxus</i> (Lucas, 1846)	0	LC	C
	<i>Monaeses pustulosus</i> Pavesi, 1895	1	LC	AE
	<i>Oxytate ribes</i> (Jézéquel, 1964)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Pherecydes tuberculatus</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1883	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Runcinia aethiops</i> (Simon, 1901) (Fig. 29)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia erythrina</i> Jézéquel, 1964	1	LC	AE
	<i>Runcinia flavida</i> (Simon, 1881)	0	LC	C
	<i>Runcinia johnstoni</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE
	<i>Simorcus cotti</i> Lessert, 1936	1	LC	AE
	<i>Synema diana</i> (Audouin, 1826) (Fig. 30)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Synema mandibulare</i> Dahl, 1907 (Fig. 31)	2	LC	AE
	<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus australis</i> Comellini, 1957 (Fig. 27)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus blandus</i> Karsch, 1880	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890 (Fig. 28)	0	LC	C
	<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE
	<i>Thomisus steningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tmarus comellinii</i> Garcia-Neto, 1989	1	LC	AE
	<i>Tmarus natalensis</i> Lessert, 1925	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Xysticus havilandi</i> Lawrence, 1942 (Fig. 32)	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Xysticus tugelanus</i> Lawrence, 1942	2	LC	STHE
Trachelidae	<i>Afrocto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Capobula montana</i> Haddad, Jin, Platnick & Booysen, 2021	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Fuchiba capensis</i> Haddad & Lyle, 2008	4	LC	SAE
Trochanteriidae	<i>Platyoides walteri</i> (Karsch, 1887)	1	LC	AE
Uloboridae	<i>Hyptiotes akermani</i> Wiehle, 1964	3	LC	SAE
	<i>Miagrammopes longicaudus</i> O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1882	2	LC	STHE
	<i>Zosis geniculata</i> (Olivier, 1789) (Fig. 36)	1	LC	C
Zodariidae	<i>Uloborus</i> *sp. new (Fig. 37)		NE	
	<i>Chariobas lineatus</i> Pocock, 1900	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Cydrela</i> sp.*		NE	
	<i>Diores poweri</i> Tucker, 1920	2	LC	STHE
Zoropsidae	<i>Procydrela procurator</i> Jocqué, 1999	4	EN	SAE
	<i>Griswoldia urbensis</i> (Lawrence, 1942) (Fig. 34)	4	LC	SAE
	<i>Phanotea xhosa</i> Griswold, 1994 (Fig. 35)	4	LC	SAE